

Hands-on Programming Session #4: Quicksort Algorithm

During this hands-on programming session, you will use `LabSorting.java` skeleton file. It's the same file as you used during the Hands-on Programming Session #2, where you implemented Bubblesort and Insertionsort with guidance.

Exercise 1 Implement one version of the Quicksort algorithm. Select the pivot as “the first element of the subarray”. This version will be one of the implementations of Quicksort used in the benchmarking part of Assignment #2.